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**NATRIURETIC FACTOR AS A MECHANISM AND
PHARMACOLOGICAL TARGET OF THE REGULATION OF WATER
AND ELECTROLYTE METABOLISM IN THE RESEARCH WORKS
OF THE BUKOVINIAN SCIENTIFIC SCHOOL**

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**НАТРИЙУРЕТИЧНИЙ ФАКТОР ЯК МЕХАНІЗМ І
ФАРМАКОЛОГІЧНА МІШЕНЬ РЕГУЛЯЦІЇ ВОДНО-
ЕЛЕКТРОЛІТНОГО ОБМІНУ В ДОСЛІДНИЦЬКИХ РОБОТАХ
БУКОВИНСЬКОЇ НАУКОВОЇ ШКОЛИ**

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**НАТРИЙУРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ФАКТОР КАК МЕХАНИЗМ И
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Summary/Резюме

The paper presents the data published by scientists of the Bukovinian Medical School obtained during the study of the functional role and pharmacology of the natriuretic factor produced by the liver. The review is devoted to the problem of ideas about the mechanisms of regulation of water-electrolyte metabolism with the participation of endogenous factors of the natriuretic system/systems. For this purpose, an analysis of the scientific literature was carried out, highlighting the features of volume regulation with an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid in the body and stimulation of volume receptors in physiological conditions and with liver pathology. The results of research conducted using the methodology of Professor Yu. I. Ivanov allow us to

conclude that, along with atrial natriuretic hormone and endogenous cardiogenic steroids, which are synthesized in the adrenal glands and hypothalamus, there are additional systems or components of individual natriuretic systems, the mechanisms of which still require additional study to determine their role in maintaining water-salt homeostasis with an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid. Natriuretic factor and endogenous digoxin-like compounds differ from natriuretic hormone, which is produced in atrial myocytes and increases glomerular filtration rate by increasing renal blood flow. This indicates that these reducers of water-electrolyte exchange have an impact not only on different mechanisms, but also on different regulatory functions.

Key words: *natriuretic factor, mechanism, pharmacological target, water and electrolyte metabolism.*

У роботі наведені опубліковані науковцями Буковинської медичної школи дані, отримані при вивченні функціональної ролі та фармакології натрійуретичного фактора, який продукується печінкою. Огляд присвячений проблемі уявлень про механізми регуляції водно-електролітного обміну за участю ендогенних чинників натрійуретичної системи/систем. Із цією метою проведено аналіз наукової літератури з висвітленням особливостей волюморегуляції при збільшенні об'єму позаклітинної рідини в організмі і стимуляції волюморекцепторів у фізіологічних умовах і при патології печінки. Результати досліджень, проведених із використанням методики професора Ю. І. Іванова, дозволяють судження про те, що разом із передсердним натрійуретичним гормоном та ендогенними кардіотонічними стероїдами, які синтезуються в наднирниках і гіпоталамусі, існують додаткові системи чи складові окремих натрійуретичних систем, механізми яких ще потребують додаткового вивчення для визначення їх ролі в підтримці водно-сольового гомеостазу при підвищенні об'єму позаклітинної рідини. Натрійуретичний фактор та ендогенні дигоксиподібні сполуки відрізняються від натрійуретичного гормону, який виробляється в міоцитах передсердь та підвищує швидкість клубочкової фільтрації за рахунок збільшення ниркового кровотоку. Це свідчить про те, що ці редуктори водно-електролітного обміну мають вплив не тільки на різні механізми, але й на різні регуляторні функції.

Ключові слова: *натрійуретичний фактор, механізм, фармакологічна мішень, водно-електролітний обмін.*

В работе представлены данные, опубликованные учеными Буковинской медицинской школы, полученные при изучении функциональной роли и фармакологии натрийуретического фактора, продуцируемого печенью. Обзор посвящен проблеме представлений о механизмах регуляции водно-электролитного обмена с участием эндогенных факторов натрийуретической системы/систем. С этой целью проведен анализ научной литературы с освещением особенностей волюморегуляции при увеличении объема внеклеточной жидкости в организме и стимуляции волюморекцепторов в физиологических условиях и патологии печени. Результаты исследований, проведенных с использованием методики профессора Ю. И. Иванова, позволяют судить о том, что вместе с передсердным натрийуретическим гормоном и эндогенными кардиотоническими стероидами, синтезируемыми в надпочечниках и гипоталамусе, существуют дополнительные системы или составляющие отдельных натрийуретических систем, приведены механизмы дополнительного изучения для определения их роли в поддержании водносолевого гомеостазу при повышении объема внеклеточной жидкости. Натрийуретический фактор и эндоген-

ные дигоксиподобные соединения отличаются от натрийуретического гормона, который производится в миоцитах предсердий и повышает скорость клубочковой фильтрации за счет увеличения почечного кровотока. Это свидетельствует о том, что эти редукторы водно-электролитного обмена оказывают влияние не только на разные механизмы, но и на разные регуляторные функции.

Ключевые слова: натрийуретический фактор, механизм, фармакологическая мишень, водно-электролитный обмен.

Until recently, it was believed that only the sympathetic nervous system, the renin-angiotensin system, and vasopressin play a key role in regulating the stability of water-salt homeostasis. So far, it has been established that next to the sodium-retaining and vasoconstrictor system there is their endogenous antagonist — the vasodilator and sodium-releasing system, which consists, at least, of atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP) and endogenous digoxin-like factor/factors.

Mineralocorticoids — aldosterone and deoxycorticosterone, vasopressin, glucocorticoids, thyroxine, insulin, glucagon, etc. are involved in the regulation of kidney functions. At the same time, the recognition that natriuresis and diuresis largely depend on the volume of extracellular fluid, the controlling function of which is to maintain the water-electrolyte balance due to changes in renal processes, did not prevent the awareness of the importance of another factor in the regulation of sodium ion excretion. The main renal mechanism for the excess of extracellular fluid is an increase in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) under the influence of ANP, which is released in response to an increase in the volume of blood entering the heart and causing stretching of the atrial walls. According to the amount of ultrafiltrate formed, tubular reabsorption decreases, as a result of which sodium ions in urine are excreted from the body [1].

A significant contribution to the elucidation of the mechanisms of the regulation of water-salt metabolism, both

in the norm and in experimental pathology, was made by Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor Yu. I. Ivanov and his colleagues at the Department of Pharmacology of the Chernivtsi Medical Institute (currently Bukovinian State Medical University). In experiments on dogs, Yu. I. Ivanov analyzed the natriuretic activity of blood flowing from the brain, kidneys, and liver and found that “hepatic” blood has the greatest natriuretic effect both under physiological conditions and after an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid. In addition, the natriuretic activity of venous blood was higher than that of arterial blood. So, Professor Yu. I. Ivanov made the assumption that in the system of natriuretic peptides — regulators of water-salt homeostasis and blood pressure circulating in the blood, there is a natriuretic factor (NF) of hepatic origin, which he also positioned as a natriuretic hormone (NH). At the same time, he developed a technique for determining NF in urine and blood plasma [2].

According to the method of Yu. I. Ivanov, laboratory white rats, which were on a hyposodium diet for a week before the experiment [3], were divided into three groups. The first group was injected intraperitoneally with 0.3 ml of 0.9 % NaCl solution (initial level); the second (control level) and the third study group — 0.3 ml of urine/blood plasma of rats before and after the salt load, respectively. After that, a 0.45 % NaCl solution in the amount of 3 % of body weight was injected into the stomach of all rats with a probe and placed in individual exchange

cages to collect urine for one hour. The excretion of sodium ions was determined in the urine of rats. The amount of NH in urine or blood plasma was calculated according to the formula:

$K = M_2M_1 - m_2m_1 / p*(M_1 - m_1)$, where:

K — amount of NH in conventional units per hour; M_1 is the average arithmetic value of Na^+ excretion in the control group after the introduction of NaCl solution; m_1 is the standard error of the arithmetic mean of this indicator; M_2 and m_2 are the corresponding values in the experimental group; p is the volume of urine/plasma that was injected.

An increase in the excretion of NF after the introduction of urine/blood plasma of rats with an increased volume of extracellular fluid by salt loading, in comparison with the initial and control data, was considered as the ability of NF to be excreted by the kidneys.

The production of NF was also stimulated by increasing the volume of extracellular fluid in other ways, in particular, by injecting a 0.85 % NaCl solution into the tail vein of rats in the amount of 30 ml/kg of body weight at a rate of 3 ml/min/100 g [4].

It is worth noting that attempts were made to find out the chemical structure of NF. It was shown that hepatic NF is a low molecular weight peptide. In order to study the chemical nature of NF, testing was carried out not only of native plasma, but also after precipitation of proteins in it with trichloroacetic acid and reaching the initial pH level. It was found that the activity of NF disappeared after precipitation of plasma proteins with trichloroacetic acid [5-8].

It was also established that the NF is characterized by species specificity, as evidenced by the quantitative and qualitative features of volume-regulatory reactions in vertebrate experimental animals of different classes — lake frogs

Rana ridibunda, white pigeons *Columba livia domestica*, white laboratory rats and purebred dogs [9].

A large number of studies by BSMU scientists were aimed at studying the mechanisms of action of NF of liver origin on the kidneys and the role of the liver, in particular NF, in the volumetric natriuretic reflex [10, 11]. Thus, it was shown that with a significant decrease in the mass of the renal parenchyma of rats, the formation of NF in response to the expansion of the extracellular space increased [12]. The content of NF in the blood plasma of rats under the conditions of an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid decreased against the background of tetrachloromethane dystrophy of the liver, with long-term administration of the hepatotoxic antibiotic chloramphenicol, and also after partial hepatectomy [13-15]. The obtained experimental data coincide with the observations of clinicians, who noted a decrease in natriuresis with an increase in the volume of extracellular fluid in patients with liver pathology [16].

At the same time, changes in volumetric natriuresis were studied in our laboratory both before and after the administration of drugs that improve the functional state of the liver. According to the obtained experimental data, choleric drugs (dehydrocholic acid, sodium selenite, flamin, etc.), potassium orotate cause a significant increase in the excretion of sodium ions, and this is due to a significant increase in the content of NF in the blood plasma of experimental animals under their influence [17-20]. Subsequent pharmacological studies established that cardioprotective, vasoactive drugs: nifedipine, verapamil, thiotriazoline mediate their renal effect through modulation of NF activity [21, 22].

Pharmacological stimulation of NF in the body is one of the mechanisms of the influence of cardiovascular and

cerebroactive drugs: xanthinol nicotinate, pentoxifyllin, thiotriazoline+pyracetam on filtration-reabsorption processes in the kidneys and absorption-secretory processes in the intestine. It was also shown that when sexually mature rats are given intravenously a 0.9 % NaCl solution in a volume of 3 % of body weight, the content of NF in the blood plasma and intestines increases, therefore the absorption of sodium ions and water in the small intestine of rats decreases, their mucosa is activated serous transport in the large intestine, the secretion of potassium ions in the intestine increases, and the renal and intestinal excretion of sodium ions is activated [23, 24].

Therefore, a retrospective analysis of studies conducted using the methodology of Professor Yu. I. Ivanov allows the conclusion that together with atrial natriuretic hormone and endogenous ouabain, which is a Na⁺,K⁺-ATPase-dependent natriuretic inhibitor of the transport systems of the renal epithelium (synthesized in the adrenal cortex and hypothalamus) [25], there are additional systems or components of a separate system endogenous digitalis-like factor (factors), the mechanisms of regulatory participation of which still require study and scientific evaluation to determine their role in maintaining water-salt homeostasis when increasing the volume of liquid in the body. It should be noted that NF and digoxin-like substances differ from ANP, which is produced in atrial myocytes and increases GFR by increasing renal blood flow. This suggests that these regulators of water-electrolyte exchange have an impact not only on different mechanisms, but also on different functions.

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